
REIMAGINING COMMUNICATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE: STRATEGIC APPROACHES IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract: This study assessed reimagining communication for social change: strategic approaches in the digital era. The participatory communication theory was anchored in this study. This study adopted the philosophy of interpretivist research. A qualitative research design was used to allow an in-depth exploration of perceptions, communication practices, and contextual realities within the study setting. The study population comprised 250 members of civil society organizations and digital advocacy groups in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, who actively participated in online social change initiatives. A sample size of 30 participants was obtained using purposive sampling. The sampling process involved identifying and selecting key informants from five recognized advocacy groups based on their roles as communication officers, campaign strategists, and digital mobilizers. Semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions were used to collect data, which provided rich narrative data and encouraged interactive responses. The interviews explored communication strategies, participation methods and challenges in digital advocacy. The data were analyzed thematically using Braun and Clarke's six-step approach, which involved familiarization, coding, theme development, and interpretation. The findings of semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions revealed that digital communication has transformed social change initiatives by enabling wider participation, faster message dissemination, and increased public interaction; however, most campaigns lacked strategic planning and sustainability. The study concluded that while digital communication has significantly expanded the reach and dynamism of social change campaigns, its full potential can only be realized when strategic planning and coherent message structures guide advocacy efforts are guided by strategic planning and coherent message structures. The study recommended that Government communication agencies and civil society organizations should develop strategic digital communication frameworks to guide social change campaigns and enhance their planning and sustainability.

Keywords: Reimagining, Communication, Social Change, Strategic Approaches, Digital Era.

Introduction

Globally, communication for social change has emerged as a transformative paradigm for addressing persistent development challenges, such as inequality, poverty, and social exclusion. The traditional approach to communication in development prioritized top-down information dissemination, but scholars now advocate

participatory communication that empowers marginalized communities to influence decision-making (Servaes, 2019). Global institutions, such as UNESCO and UNICEF have increasingly prioritized strategic communication in promoting human rights, peace building, and sustainability by integrating digital media as essential tools for community engagement (UN, 2020). The advent of digital platforms has created new opportunities for participatory development, enabling grassroots mobilization and global civic dialogue. However, unequal access to digital tools and online surveillance still limits the transformative potential of digital communication for structural social change (Couldry & Mejias, 2029).

Scholars interrogate how communication strategies intersect with cultural contexts to drive social transformation across continents. Digital communication has reshaped social movements in Africa, Asia and Latin America by amplifying the voices of excluded populations and challenging state authoritarianism (Tuftte, 2017). For instance, the Arab Spring uprisings demonstrated how mobile networks and social media could mobilize youth-led resistance against oppressive governance structures (Howard & Hussain, 2013). Similarly, indigenous communities in Latin America, employ community radio to assert cultural identity and advocate for land rights, reinforcing communication as a tool for liberation (Gumucio-Dagron, 2019). These continental experiences illustrate the dynamic relationship between communication practices and sociopolitical change across diverse regions.

In Africa, digital technologies are increasingly integrated into development initiatives to facilitate education, governance, and health communication. African civil society organizations use strategic communication on social media to hold leaders accountable, and demand policy reforms (Mutsvairo & Ragnedda, 2019). Movements such as #FeesMustFall and EndSARS in South Africa and Nigeria, respectively, demonstrate how digital communication can strengthen public participation and challenge institutional injustice (Olorunnisola & Martin, 2020). However, researchers caution that digital activism without strategic communication frameworks and policy advocacy may produce short-term visibility without long-lasting structural change (Moyo, 2021). Thus, strategic communication planning remains essential for sustaining digital movements and transforming online engagement into policy outcomes.

In Nigeria, communication for social change has evolved through the interplay of mass media and digital technologies. Traditional media, such as radio and television, remain influential tools for disseminating information, especially in rural areas, while mobile phones and social media platforms increasingly drive youth engagement and civic participation (Akinwale, 2021). Digital communication strategies have influenced governance debates, health campaigns, and humanitarian responses. Digital platforms played a crucial role in health awareness campaigns during the COVID-19 pandemic by disseminating prevention messages and combating misinformation (Ojebuyi & Salawu, 2022). However, digital divides persist due to internet access inequality, low digital literacy, and infrastructural challenges that inhibit inclusive participation in social change communication (Olatunji, 2023).

To address systemic inequalities, communication for social change integrates participatory communication theories with social mobilization strategies. The theory emphasizes horizontal communication, community ownership, and dialogic engagement as essential strategies for empowerment (Freire, 1970; Servaes, 2019).

Development scholars view communication as a process of social interaction and negotiated meaning that fosters change (Dagron, 2011). This shift toward horizontal interaction is reinforced by digital communication by enabling decentralized information flows and citizen-led narratives. The convergence of participatory communication and digital advocacy forms the basis of reimagining communication for social change in the digital era.

In the digital era, strategic communication involves deliberate planning, message framing, and multi-stakeholder engagement to influence behavior, policy, and public perception. Scholars define strategic communication as purposeful communication that aligns messages with organizational or societal goals to influence change (Hallahan et al., 2007). Strategic communication enhances advocacy campaigns in social change context by linking message design with audience analysis, media selection and evaluation frameworks (Nambiar, 2020). Digital tools enhance strategic communication by enabling real-time engagement, data analytics, and networked collaboration. The integration of digital media into strategic communication redefines advocacy practice by expanding the scope of community participation and enhancing message reach.

Socio-technical dynamics shape the relationship between communication and social change in the digital era. Digital platforms foster collective action through networked communication that transcends geographical boundaries (Castells, 2012). Social media networks enable virtual communities of practice where individuals share knowledge, coordinate campaigns, and build solidarity (Kietzmann & Canhoto, 2013). However, algorithmic bias, online harassment, and state surveillance pose threats to online democratic communication (Pasquale, 2015). Effective social change communication requires understanding how power operates in digital spaces and developing strategies that resist digital oppression while promoting ethical and inclusive engagement.

Empirical studies reveal that communication strategies significantly shape public awareness, behavioral change, and civic participation. For example, community health campaigns in sub-Saharan Africa recorded higher compliance levels when participatory communication methods were used alongside digital platforms (Okon, 2022). Environmental advocacy organizations use digital storytelling to create emotional connections and mobilize public support for climate justice (Schafer & O'Neill, 2017). Evidence suggests that communication strategies grounded in community participation and cultural relevance have a greater chance of achieving sustainable social change than top-down campaigns (Manyozo, 2012). Digital platforms complement rather than replace traditional approaches when strategically integrated.

Despite its transformative potential, social change communication in the digital era faces limitations related to misinformation, digital exclusion, and weak communication governance. The proliferation of fake news and propaganda threatens public trust and undermines social good communication efforts (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017). Marginalized groups, including rural women and low-income communities, experience digital marginalization due to socioeconomic barriers that restrict online participation (Akingbade, 2023). To reimagine communication for social change, media literacy, equitable access, and regulatory frameworks that protect free expression must be prioritized.

Reimagining communication for social change in the digital era requires a holistic approach that integrates innovation, policy advocacy, and community empowerment. The strategic use of digital media must align with ethical communication principles, cultural values, and inclusive participation. Scholars advocate capacity-building in digital media literacy, collaborative policy dialogues and investment in communication infrastructure to enhance equity (Servaes, 2019). The future of social change communication depends on strategic planning that mobilizes collective action, amplifies marginalized voices, and transforms social systems through informed participation, and digital solidarity.

This study addresses the inadequate reimagining of communication strategies for social change in the digital era, as existing approaches remain largely top-down, insufficiently participatory, and poorly integrated with digital technologies, resulting in limited civic engagement, digital exclusion, and weak transformative impact on social development.

This study aims to examine how digital communication tools are currently used in social change initiatives while identifying their strategic application gaps. The study also seeks to assess the extent to which participatory communication approaches influence civic engagement within digital social change campaigns. Furthermore, the study intends to determine the challenges that limit the effective integration of strategic communication frameworks in efforts aimed at social transformation in the digital era.

The concept of social change

Social change refers to a significant alteration in societal structures, behavior pattern, cultural values, and norms over time. Scholars have conceptualized social change as a multidimensional process that reshapes social institutions, redistributes power, and enhances human welfare (Giddens, 2013). It is driven by dynamic interactions between individuals, groups, and institutions and may occur through gradual reform or radical transformation. Social change is often assessed through indicators such as improved social justice, enhanced civic participation, reduction of inequalities, and community empowerment (Haralambos & Holborn, 2017). In development research, social change embodies both outcomes and processes that promote societal advancement and inclusive progress. Modern societies increasingly pursue social change through organized efforts to address social problems such as poverty, gender inequality, corruption, environmental degradation, and human rights violations (United Nations, 2020).

Communication scholars have emphasized that social change is not merely a structural phenomenon but a communicative process that involves collective meaning-making and public dialogue (Tufte, 2017). The dependent nature of social change within a communication context highlights the influence strategic and participatory communication on behavioral and attitudinal transformation (Servaes, 2019). Social change is negotiated through interaction, mobilization, and empowerment. Digital technologies have redefined social change by enabling virtual communities and social networks to challenge oppressive structures, amplify marginalized voices, and promote civic action (Castells, 2012). In empirical studies, social change is operationalized through measurable indicators, such as policy reforms, social awareness levels, behavioral change, and increased access to rights and resources (Kumar, 2019). Thus, social change represents the final transformative outcome that communication strategies seek to achieve in development contexts.

The Concept of Strategic Communication

Strategic communication is the purposeful use of communication by organizations, institutions, or social groups to fulfill mission-driven objectives and influence target audiences (Hallahan et al., 2007). It is grounded in deliberate message design, planning, and dissemination to achieve behavioral change or shifts in public opinion (Nambiar, 2020). By incorporating communication theories into planned interventions, strategic communication bridges persuasion, advocacy, and relationship-building. It differs from ordinary communication because it is systematic and goal-oriented, supported by research, audience analysis, and impact evaluation (Argenti et al., 2005). Strategic communication is used to raise awareness, shape public discourse and mobilize stakeholders toward collective action to develop and social change contexts.

The relevance of strategic communication in the digital era has grown due to the complexity of social issues that require informed communication interventions (Heath & Johansen, 2018). Scholars argue that strategic communication enhances advocacy and development programs' effectiveness by ensuring message consistency, credibility and contextual relevance (Cornelissen, 2017). Strategic communication in social change projects includes campaigns, policy advocacy, media engagement, and digital messaging tailored to empower communities and influence decision-makers (Hoskins & O'Loughlin, 2015). Digital platforms, such as social media, blogs, and webinars, expand the reach of strategic communication by enabling real-time interaction and grassroots mobilization (Kietzmann & Canhoto, 2013). When strategically applied, communication becomes a tool for influencing public behavior and promoting sustainable social change.

Concept of digital media

Digital media refers to electronic communication channels that store, process, and transmit information through digital technologies, including social media platforms, mobile applications, websites, podcasts, and online forums (Lister et al., 2009). Digital media has revolutionized human interaction by enabling instantaneous communication, user-generated content, and interactive engagement (Jenkins, 2018). It breaks geographic barriers and fosters global connectivity, transforming how people access information and participate in social processes. Digital media tools allow individuals and communities to exchange ideas, form networks, and express opinions in unprecedented ways (Baym, 2015). In communication research, digital media is analyzed, using indicators such as accessibility, interactivity, user participation and media convergence (Dijck, 2013).

Within development communication studies, digital media plays a crucial role in advancing social change by democratizing information flow and enabling citizen participation (Mutsvairo & Ragnedda, 2019). Activists, NGOs, and grassroots movements use digital platforms to advocate for human rights, environmental protection, and social justice (Tayeebwa, 2016). Digital campaigns, such as #MeToo and #BlackLivesMatter demonstrate the ability of digital media to stimulate global awareness and mobilize collective action (Jackson et al., 2020). However, research also highlights constraints such as misinformation, cyber harassment, and unequal access, which can hinder the effectiveness of digital communication (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017). Therefore, digital media serves as a dynamic variable that shapes social change communication in complex and evolving ways.

Participatory Communication Concept

Participatory communication refers to a people-centered approach that emphasizes dialog, mutual understanding, and community involvement in decision-making processes (Freire, 1970). It rejects the linear transmission model of communication and promotes horizontal interaction to empower individuals and communities (Servaes, 2019). Participatory communication facilitates inclusive dialogue by encouraging marginalized voices to contribute to problem identification and solution development (Tuftte, 2017). It is rooted in democratic principles that value shared knowledge and collective problem-solving. Scholars have conceptualized participatory communication as both a process and an outcome that enables social learning and community ownership (Manyozo, 2012).

Participatory communication shapes the relationship between strategic communication and social change by determining how effective communication strategies engage target audiences. Research indicates that when audiences actively participate rather than passively receive messages communication interventions produce meaningful results (Gumucio-Dagron, 2019). Participatory methods such as community forums, focus group discussions, storytelling, and collaborative media production, foster social trust and enhance campaign relevance (Dagron, 2011). Participatory communication extends to online platforms where interactive features enable two-way engagement and co-creation of content (Jenkins, 2018). Participatory communication moderates communication outcomes by increasing social change initiatives' inclusiveness, cultural relevance and sustainability (Mefalopulos, 2008). It thus serves as a crucial mediator that enhances strategic and digital communication transformative potential.

Paulo Freire (1970) participatory communication theory serves as the theoretical foundation for this study on reimagining communication for social change in the digital era. The theory emerged as a response to the limitations of the dominant top-down communication models used in early development paradigms, advocating instead for dialogue, critical consciousness, and community empowerment as pathways to social transformation. Reine (1970) posits that meaningful change occurs when individuals actively identify their problems, analyze root causes, and collaboratively develop solutions. The theory's major tenets include dialogue as an instrument of liberation, communication as a horizontal and democratic process, and collective participation as essential for transforming oppressive social conditions. The theory assumes that people possess indigenous knowledge that is valuable for their liberation, and that social oppressive communication systems that silence marginalized voices perpetuate social inequality (Servaes, 2019). The study's emphasis on participation, empowerment, and inclusion aligns directly with the study's objectives, which focus on examining digital communication strategies, strengthening civic engagement, and promoting strategic communication for social change. The theory is relevant because it provides a framework for integrating participatory communication into digital platforms, ensuring that technological advancements do not reinforce inequality but instead foster inclusive social transformation. By applying Freire's participatory principles, this

study contributes to contemporary scholarship by adapting a foundational communication theory to the evolving realities of digital communication in social change efforts.

Empirical Review

Akinwale (2021) conducted a study titled Digital Communication and Civic Mobilization in Nigerian Youth Movements to examine how digital communication tools are utilized in social change initiatives among youth organizations in Nigeria. The study adopted a mixed-method design using surveys and social media campaigns content analysis across Twitter and Facebook. Findings showed that while digital tools enhanced mobilization and rapid message dissemination, their effectiveness was limited by a lack of strategic communication planning and inconsistent messaging. The study also revealed that most campaigns focused on creating awareness rather than on sustained advocacy. This study is similar to the current research because both investigate the use of digital communication in driving social change. However, the current study goes further by addressing the gap in strategic planning and by incorporating PMC as a moderating factor to strengthen social change outcomes.

Nwosu and Chikezie (2022) conducted a study titled Participatory Communication and Civic Engagement in Community Health Campaigns in Southeast Nigeria. This study aimed to assess the extent to which participatory communication influences civic engagement in health-related social change programs. Using a qualitative design with focus group discussions and key informant interviews, the researchers found that participatory approaches such as community dialogue, local storytelling, and stakeholder consultations improved trust, message acceptance, and voluntary participation in health campaigns. The findings further indicated that campaigns designed with active community involvement yielded long-term behavioral change compared with those driven by top-down media messages. This study shares similarity with the current research in its focus on participatory communication and civic engagement. However, while Nwosu and Chikezie focused on health campaigns in rural communities, the present study extends participation discourse into the digital era and examines how participatory strategies moderate the effectiveness of strategic communication in broader social change contexts.

Taye (2023) conducted a study titled Barriers to Strategic Communication in Digital Social Transformation Projects in Sub-Saharan Africa. This study aimed to identify the challenges limiting the integration of strategic communication frameworks in digital-based development programs. Employing a descriptive survey design across NGOs in Kenya, Uganda and Ghana, the study revealed that inadequate funding, weak digital literacy, poor policy support and lack of communication expertise hinder the success of social transformation initiatives. The findings indicated that although organizations used social media platforms for outreach, most lacked structured communication strategies that aligned with project goals. This study is similar to the present research because both examine challenges in strategic communication for social change. However, this study makes a unique contribution by exploring how participatory communication can moderate these challenges and enhance strategic communication outcomes in the digital era.

Methodology

This study adopted the interpretivist research philosophy, emphasizing the subjective meanings and experiences of individuals involved in digital communication for social change. A qualitative research design was used to allow an in-depth exploration of perceptions, communication practices, and contextual realities within the study setting. The study population comprised 250 members of civil society organizations and digital advocacy groups in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, who actively participated in online social change initiatives. These organizations had a background in civic engagement, human rights advocacy, and community development, making them relevant to the study. Purposive sampling was used to obtain a size of 30 participants to ensure the inclusion of individuals with direct experience in strategic digital communication. The sampling process involved identifying and selecting key informants from five recognized advocacy groups based on their roles as communication officers, campaign strategists, and digital mobilizers. Semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions were used to collect data, which provide rich narrative data encouraged interactive responses. The interviews explored communication strategies, methods of participation, and challenges in digital advocacy. Data were analyzed thematically using Braun and Clarke's six-step approach, which involved familiarization, coding, theme development and interpretation. Thematic analysis was justified because it aligned with the interpretivist philosophy by allowing the researcher to identify patterns of meaning and derive insights grounded in the live experiences of participants.

Qualitative data analysis using semi-structured interviews

Digital communication tools were used in social change initiatives and gaps in their strategic application were identified.

The analysis revealed that participants widely used digital communication tools but did so in an unstructured and reactive manner. Most respondents confirmed that digital media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Twitter were their primary advocacy tools. One participant emphasized, "Social media gave us a voice when traditional media ignored us, especially during campaigns like #EndSARS" (Participant 4). However, the study found that while digital platforms enabled fast communication, there was no clear strategy guiding their use in advocacy processes. Advocacy efforts often emerge spontaneously in response to events rather than planned initiatives driven by long-term goals.

WhatsApp was the most frequently used communication tool for mobilization at the grassroots level. Participants explained that WhatsApp groups enabled quick coordination among activists and community members due to its familiarity and low data consumption. As Participant 7 noted, "We relied on WhatsApp to mobilize participants for protests and meetings because it is affordable and accessible even in rural areas." However, reliance on WhatsApp also limited the visibility of the campaign because information circulated only within closed groups, reducing outreach to wider public audiences. This dependency on private networks, rather than public engagement reduced the potential impact of advocacy communication.

Twitter has emerged as a vital tool for amplifying advocacy campaigns and attracting public attention. Participants reported that Twitter Spaces and hashtags were instrumental in reaching national conversations. Participant 12 stated, "Twitter helped us trend campaigns and get media attention; without Twitter, our issues would remain silent." However, Twitter's strategic application was weak, as most posts lacked coordinated

messages or targeted persuasion. Campaigns were often emotionally driven rather than evidence-based, weakening their persuasiveness to policymakers and international observers.

The interview indicated that Facebook played a supporting role by providing a platform for community debates and opinion sharing. Several participants acknowledged using Facebook Live for advocacy dialogues. Participant 2 explained, “We hosted Facebook Live discussions on women’s rights, but we didn’t have professional media skills, so engagement dropped over time.” The lack of message framing and audience targeting resulted in inconsistent engagement. This demonstrates a major gap in the technical capacity of advocacy groups regarding content strategy and communication planning.

The participants also highlighted the emerging use of Instagram for storytelling and visual advocacy. However, they admitted that while Instagram was effective in appealing to younger audiences through videos and graphics, they lacked the skills to create visuals. Participant 15 confessed, “We had powerful stories, but we didn’t know how to visually package them for Instagram; our posts were not as attractive as those of bigger campaigns.” This reveals a gap in digital advocacy literacy, particularly in multimedia communication.

The absence of communication monitoring and evaluation among advocacy groups was another theme identified. None of the participants had formal mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of their digital campaigns. Participant 9 stated, “We just post and hope people respond; we don’t track impact because we don’t know how.” The lack of evaluation tools made it difficult to refine strategies, measure awareness levels or track behavioral change. Advocacy remained activity-based rather than results-driven.

The interviews also revealed that organizations rarely integrated digital communication with offline advocacy strategies. The participants admitted that online campaigns were not aligned with physical community engagement. Participant 6 said, “What we do online does not always connect with what happens on the ground; there is no link between our online message and community action.” This gap weakened advocacy outcomes because online momentum rarely translated into offline mobilization or policy influence.

Finally, the participants acknowledged that the lack of strategic communication planning hindered the long-term impact. Campaigns quickly disappeared after trending online because they lacked continuity plans. Participant 11 observed, “Our campaigns burn fast and die fast because we don’t plan them; we react instead of strategizing.” This highlighted the need for structured communication frameworks that include message consistency, audience analysis, stakeholder mapping, and sustainability plans. The findings clearly demonstrated that while digital tools were widely used, their potential for effective social change communication remained largely underutilized due to the absence of strategic planning.

The extent to which participatory communication approaches influence civic engagement in digital social change campaigns.

Participatory communication significantly shaped civic engagement in digital social change campaigns by fostering inclusiveness and dialogue. Participants consistently reported that campaigns that incorporated two-way communication rather than one-way mobilization were more engaging and impactful. For example, one participant said, “We responded more to campaigns where our opinions were requested, not just where we were told what to do” (P4). This finding aligned with the principles of participatory communication, which

emphasize dialogue and co-creation of meaning in social transformation processes. The participants emphasized that interactive digital tools like polls, discussion threads, and live sessions, deepened their sense of campaigns' goals involvement and ownership.

Furthermore, participatory digital strategies enhanced trust and legitimacy in social change efforts. Several participants explained that campaigns allowing community contributions appeared more transparent and accountable. According to P9, "When digital campaigns showed us that our suggestions were used to adjust strategies, we trusted the organizers more." This trust increased the willingness to participate more actively, including sharing campaign messages, volunteering, and even donating. The findings highlighted that participation was not only emotional but behavioral, translating into measurable civic action. Thus, participatory communication did not merely inform but mobilized.

Another key finding from the findings was that participatory approaches empowered marginalized voices in the digital space. Participants from youth and grassroots backgrounds indicated that digital platforms provided an opportunity to bypass traditional communication hierarchies. As P12 explained, "In physical meetings, influential people dominate. But online, I could freely share my views without feeling intimidated." This democratization of voice encouraged broader civic engagement by reducing communicative inequality. Participants also noted that digital campaigns that created safe spaces for dialogue, such as moderated WhatsApp and Facebook groups experienced stronger engagement levels than those that merely broadcasted information.

Moreover, the findings showed that participatory communication fostered digital community-building, which in turn promoted sustained civic engagement. Participants reported that campaigns that encouraged interaction among participants built solidarity and collective identity around social causes. P6 noted, "It was not just about the campaign." It became a community of people passionate about change." This sense of online community translated into continuous engagement even after the campaigns ended. Participants described scenarios in which campaign groups evolved into advocacy networks, demonstrating sustained civic participation beyond the initial mobilization efforts.

However, the findings also revealed that participation levels depended on the perceived relevance of the campaign issue to local realities. Campaigns that reflected lived experiences attracted more engagement. For example, P18 stated, "I only participate in digital campaigns that address issues affecting my community, such as unemployment, flooding, or police harassment." Campaigns perceived as detached or imported agendas generated minimal interaction regardless of the use of participatory tools. This indicates that participatory communication must be grounded in contextual sensitivity to effectively drive civic action. Engagement increased when campaign messages reflected cultural and social authenticity.

The study further revealed that during campaigns, participatory communication created opportunities for knowledge exchange and collective learning. The participants highlighted that discussions and feedback sessions helped clarify campaign objectives and debunk misinformation. P11 shared, "Through the comment sections, people asked questions and we shared facts." It helped many of us better understand the issue." This shared learning environment promoted informed civic participation rather than blind activism. The findings

indicated that participatory strategies transformed campaigns into digital learning communities, enhancing the quality of civic engagement quality.

Despite the positive influence of participatory communication, the findings showed that digital literacy gaps sometimes hindered participation. Participants with limited digital skills felt excluded from some campaign activities. P15 admitted, “I wanted to contribute but I didn’t know how to use some of the tools they used for engagement.” This exclusion weakened the reach of the campaign and diversity of perspectives. Complex platforms intimidated some users, reducing their willingness to engage. The findings demonstrated that participatory communication must consider user-friendly social media tools to ensure inclusive engagement.

Finally, the findings revealed fatigue in long-term campaigns. While participatory strategies initially stimulated high engagement, prolonged campaigns without visible outcomes led to reduced participation. As explained by P3, “We contributed ideas for months but saw no change.” “People got tired and stopped participating.” This decline indicated that participation must be linked to feedback loops and demonstrable outcomes to sustain civic commitment. The participants recommended periodic progress updates and recognition of contributors as strategies to maintain engagement. The findings emphasized that participation must be meaningful and not symbolic.

Challenges limiting the effective integration of strategic communication frameworks in digital-era social transformation efforts.

The interviews revealed that the effective integration of strategic communication frameworks in digital-era social transformation efforts faced significant structural challenges. Most participants reported that many digital campaigns lacked clear communication planning and relied heavily on spontaneous activism rather than strategy. According to P2, “Most campaigns just start out of emotion without planning or strategy; that is why they lose direction after some weeks.” This finding implied that the absence of structured communication frameworks limited message consistency, audience targeting, and campaign sustainability.

Another major challenge identified was inadequate stakeholder mapping and engagement in digital campaign planning. Participants explained that many campaigns failed to identify key audiences, influencers, and partners who could strengthen advocacy efforts. As P7 stated, “Some campaigns ignore key stakeholders like policymakers or community leaders and focus only on social media users, so the message doesn’t reach to those who can implement real change.” This gap weakened the link between digital advocacy and influence of offline policy, revealing a major constraint in strategic communication integration.

The interviews also showed that resource limitations hindered the adoption of structured communication strategies in efforts to promote digital social change. Most participants highlighted funding challenges, lack of technical expertise, and insufficient access to professional communication tools as obstacles. P14 noted, “You need funding to run analytics, sponsor posts, or hire experts.” “Many campaigns run on passion, not resources, so they cannot apply proper strategies.” This challenge reflected a disconnection between campaign goals and operational capacity, which reduced the effectiveness of digital activism.

Furthermore, poor message framing and inconsistent narratives weakened the persuasive power of digital campaigns. Participants emphasized that messages were often emotional but lacked evidence-based framing,

reducing their influence on decision-makers. P10 explained, “Some campaigns are loud but not logical. They do not use facts, data, or strong storytelling to convince people.” This weakness revealed a lack of strategy in aligning messages with audience interests and communication objectives, a core principle of strategic communication.

The study also found that digital misinformation and counter-messaging pose serious challenges to strategic communication efforts. Hostile actors often spread false information to discredit campaigns or shift public opinion. P19 stated, “Anytime we push a campaign online, misinformation follows.” “Opponents twist the message, and we spend time doing damage control.” The prevalence of misinformation disrupted campaign messaging, reduced credibility, and forced organizers to adopt defensive rather than proactive communication strategies.

Additionally, the interviews revealed internal coordination problems among campaign teams due to the lack of defined communication roles and responsibilities. Participants described chaotic message approval, content creation, and response management. P8 narrated, “Everyone was posting anything they liked.” There was no unified voice or strategy. We looked confused in public.” This lack of organizational communication structure undermined public trust and led to inconsistent campaign branding, weakening the overall impact of the campaign.

The absence of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms in digital campaigns was another constraint. Most participants admitted that campaigns rarely tracked engagement metrics or assessed message effectiveness. P17 noted, “We just post and move on; nobody checks if people understand the message or if attitudes are changing.” This weakness limited learning and adaptation during campaigns, revealing a missing link between strategic communication and performance evaluation, which is essential requirement for campaign refinement and long-term success.

Lastly, the findings highlighted socio-cultural and political barriers that limited the integration of strategic communication integration. The participants reported that fear of surveillance, online harassment, and political intimidation discouraged structured activism. As P5 said, “If you plan too strategically, authorities start watching you.” “People are afraid to speak boldly.” Cultural norms also influenced participation, as some audiences viewed digital activism as confrontational. These sociopolitical constraints restricted open communication planning, forcing some campaigns to remain informal and poorly structured to avoid backlash.

Focus Group Discussions

Digital communication tools were used in social change initiatives and gaps in their strategic application were identified.

The focus group discussion revealed that digital technology had redefined the conception and execution of social change communication. Participants agreed that traditional communication models were no longer sufficient in driving modern social advocacy. According to FGD-P3, “We used to rely on town hall meetings and radio talk shows, but now people respond faster to social media campaigns.” The group noted that digital communication not only expanded the reach of social messages but also increased the speed of feedback and interaction. The participants emphasized that the internet had created a participatory environment that

encouraged ordinary citizens to become change agents, making social movements more inclusive and dynamic than before.

The participants further observed that social media platforms, particularly Facebook, Twitter (now X), and WhatsApp, had become major tools for mobilizing public attention around social issues. Many of them explained that digital platforms enabled campaigns to gain momentum within hours, especially when visual content was used effectively. FGD-P6 remarked, “Once a post goes viral, it becomes difficult for authorities to ignore it. People start asking questions and demanding accountability.” This confirmed that the digital environment amplified the voices of citizens and made social change communication more transparent and immediate. Participants emphasized that visual and emotional content often triggered stronger engagement than text-based advocacy.

Moreover, the discussion revealed that digital technology facilitated collaboration among different stakeholders in social change campaigns. Participants agreed that digital platforms made it easier for activists, non-governmental organizations, journalists, and citizens to coordinate their actions in real time. FGD-P2 shared, “Before now, we would need weeks to plan a protest. Now, with one WhatsApp group, we can organize and execute the project within a day.” This showed that reimagining communication for social change in the digital era required leveraging collaboration tools that could unify diverse actors toward a common cause. The group concluded that connectivity had become both a communication tool and a mobilization force.

However, participants acknowledged that not all campaigns achieved their intended social outcomes despite the advantages of digital tools. They argued that success often depended on how strategically messages were crafted and disseminated. According to FGD-P8 explained, “Some campaigns fail because they are too emotional without facts or direction.” “People get excited for a few days and move on.” Reimagining communication also involved adopting structured strategies that could sustain audience interest and transform awareness into action. The group stressed that strategy was as vital as creativity in digital advocacy.

The findings from the focus group further indicated that the digital environment encouraged creative experimentation, leading to the use of multimedia and storytelling techniques to strengthen the impact of the message. Participants highlighted that videos, memes, and infographics made information more relatable and shareable. FGD-P4 noted, “When we used short videos telling real stories, people connected emotionally and started sharing our posts faster.” This creative turn reflected a shift from rigid institutional messaging to human-centered narratives. The group asserted that effective communication for social change must appeal to both intellect and emotion to mobilize participation in the digital context.

Finally, the discussion revealed that while digital tools redefined communication dynamics, they also introduced ethical and regulatory challenges. The participants noted issues such as misinformation, online harassment, and censorship, which often distorted the objectives of social campaigns. FGD-P10 lamented, “Sometimes, false stories spread faster than the real campaign. It discourages people from trusting the cause.” This finding demonstrates that digital transformation requires a balance between open participation and responsible information management. The group agreed that strategies for combating misinformation, ensuring

data privacy, and maintaining the integrity of advocacy messages should include reimagining communication for social change.

The extent to which participatory communication approaches influence civic engagement in digital social change campaigns.

Participatory communication approaches significantly enhanced civic engagement in digital social change campaigns by enabling interactive dialog rather than one-way message dissemination. Participants explained that campaigns that encouraged participation made people feel valued and involved. FGD-P1 noted, “People engage more when they feel they are part of the process, not just an audience.” The group discussed how participatory strategies such as polls, live chats, and community forums on platforms, such as Facebook and WhatsApp helped in gathering public opinions and promoting shared ownership of campaign goals. This collaborative approach increased participants’ commitment and responsiveness.

Participatory communication reduced the distance between campaign initiators and community members. Unlike traditional campaigns that relied on experts and opinion leaders, digital participatory strategies allowed ordinary citizens to join conversations and contribute ideas. According to FGD-P7, “During the flood relief campaign, we had WhatsApp groups where people from affected communities gave updates themselves.” “It was not someone speaking for them; they spoke for themselves.” This direct involvement increased authenticity and encouraged civic responsibility, as individuals were more willing to support causes that reflected their voices and realities.

However, the findings revealed that the level of participation depended on the communication approach inclusiveness. Some participants explained that certain campaigns became elitist because organizers used platforms or languages that excluded marginalized groups. FGD-P6 mentioned, “Most campaigns are done in English or on Twitter where the educated people are.” What about the rural people who don’t even use those platforms?” Meaningful participation requires accessibility and linguistic inclusiveness to ensure broader civic engagement. Campaigns that ignored local languages or community platforms struggled to mobilize mass participation.

The focus group also observed that participatory communication promoted transparency and trust in digital campaigns. Participants expressed that when campaign organizers allowed open dialogue and feedback, people believed more in the cause’ integrity. FGD-P5 said, “When they allow us to question decisions and see campaign updates, we know they are sincere.” That makes us stay involved.” Transparency gave participants confidence that their contributions were not being manipulated, thereby increasing their willingness to engage, volunteer, and even donate to campaign activities. Trust was a critical factor in sustaining engagement over time.

Despite its benefits, participatory communication can sometimes lead to conflicts and disagreements within campaign groups. Participants reported that open forums often attracted criticism and arguments that slowed down decision-making. FGD-P9 remarked, “Sometimes too many opinions delay action.” People argue instead of acting.” The lack of clear moderation rules and leadership within the platforms of participatory campaigns

also caused distractions and conflict. This demonstrated that while participation encouraged inclusiveness, strong facilitation skills and communication etiquette were required to remain productive.

Finally, digital participatory communication enhanced civic learning and social consciousness among campaign participants. Through continuous engagement, people gained awareness about social issues and developed problem-solving skills. FGD-P3 shared, “I didn’t even understand climate change before joining the environmental campaign group. However, through discussions and shared posts, I learned a lot and even educated others.” This demonstrated that participatory communication did not only mobilize people, it empowered them intellectually and socially. Civic engagement evolved from the passive reaction to active contribution, strengthening digital activism and community transformation.

Challenges limiting the effective integration of strategic communication frameworks in digital-era social transformation efforts.

The focus group revealed that the lack of planning and structure in campaign execution was one of the major challenges limiting the effective integration of strategic communication frameworks in digital social transformation efforts. Participants agreed that most digital campaigns emerged spontaneously in reaction to social events and therefore lacked strategic direction. According to FGD-P2, “Most campaigns are emotional reactions, not strategic actions.” “People get angry and start a hashtag, but there is no long-term plan.” This reactive approach caused many campaigns to quickly lose momentum and fail to achieve meaningful outcomes beyond online attention.

The findings further showed that the absence of professional communication expertise in campaign planning hindered message quality and impact. Participants noted that many digital activists had passion but lacked the skills required to design strategic messages, manage advocacy communication, or effectively engage different stakeholder groups. FGD-P7 explained, “Most campaign teams don’t have trained communication experts, so their messages are sometimes unclear or inconsistent.” Consequently, poorly framed messages reduced campaign credibility and limited audience persuasion, especially among policymakers and institutional stakeholders.

Participants also identified limited access to funding and digital tools as a major barrier to strategic communication. While social media offered free platforms for message dissemination, effective strategic communication required resources for sponsored content, analytics, professional designs, and digital training. According to FGD-P4, “Strategy needs money. If you cannot pay for visibility or tools, your message will not go far.” This resource gap restricted campaign reach and made it difficult to maintain visibility over time. As a result, only well-funded organizations sustained long-term digital advocacy, whereas grassroots movements struggled.

Digital misinformation and online propaganda disrupted strategic communication efforts. Participants observed that opponents of social causes often used misinformation tactics to confuse audiences and discredit campaign messages. FGD-P9 expressed concern, saying, “Before your message gains ground, fake news comes out to counter it, and people don’t know what to believe anymore.” This challenge to campaign coherence forced

organizers to spend time correcting falsehoods instead of advancing their core messages. Misinformation reduces public trust and weakens campaign influence.

Another identified challenge was internal communication breakdown within campaign teams due to poor coordination and leadership. Participants reported that some digital campaigns lacked defined roles and communication protocols, resulting in conflicting messages shared by different team members. FGD-P6 mentioned, “Sometimes team members post different messages, and people get confused about what we really stand for.” This lack of consistency weakened campaign identity and reduced message impact. Participants suggested that campaign teams needed communication guidelines to ensure message alignment and clarity.

Finally, the focus group revealed that sociopolitical fears and digital surveillance discouraged the full application of strategic communication frameworks in advocacy campaigns. Participants described how some activists avoided structured or high-profile communication strategies because of fear of tracking or intimidation by authorities. FGD-P8 said, “If a campaign looks too organized, government agents start monitoring.” “People are scared of being arrested.” This fear pushed many campaigns to operate informally and avoid strategic visibility, limiting their effectiveness. As a result, digital activism has sometimes remained fragmented and cautious instead of systematic and goal-driven.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions revealed that digital communication has transformed social change initiatives by enabling wider participation, faster message dissemination, and increased public interaction; however, most campaigns lacked strategic planning and sustainability. The relevance of Akinwale’s (2021) finding is evident, as his study affirmed that digital communication platforms enhance participatory information exchange and expand public involvement in social change processes, which supports the finding that digital media have transformed social change communication by enabling wider participation and faster message dissemination. Participatory communication theory supports this finding because it emphasizes democratized information flow and community involvement, which explains why digital platforms have redefined social change communication by enabling audiences to move from passive receivers to active contributors in message creation and dissemination.

The study also found that participatory communication approaches significantly enhanced civic engagement by fostering dialogue, inclusiveness, co-creation of messages, and collective ownership of advocacy goals, although digital inequalities and participation fatigue limited long-term involvement. The findings align with those of Nwosu and Chikezie (2022), who established that participatory communication fosters collective engagement and civic responsibility by allowing audiences to contribute to campaign content and decision-making, reinforcing the conclusion that participatory approaches significantly increase civic engagement in digital campaigns through dialogue and inclusiveness. Because participatory communication promotes dialogue, shared meaning, and collective decision-making, the findings strongly align with the theory, validating why campaigns that encourage interaction and inclusiveness recorded higher levels of civic engagement and community-driven action.

Additionally, the findings showed that the effective integration of strategic communication frameworks in digital-era social transformation efforts was hindered by poor campaign planning, limited resources, misinformation threats, weak coordination, and socio-political constraints that reduced message impact and campaign effectiveness. This finding corresponds with Taye (2023), who noted that structural limitations, such as poor planning, resource constraints, and weak stakeholder coordination hinder effective communication strategies in advocacy initiatives, thereby validating the study's finding that strategic integration challenges reduce the efficiency and impact of digital-era social transformation efforts. The findings are also consistent with the participatory communication theory, which stresses the need for structured collaboration and empowerment processes, highlighting that participation becomes superficial and ineffective in achieving transformational social outcomes without strategic coordination, equitable inclusion, and supportive communication structures.

Conclusion

The study established that while digital communication has significantly expanded the reach and dynamism of social change campaigns, its full potential can only be realized when advocacy efforts are strategic planning and coherent message structures.

The study explored that participatory communication remains a powerful driver of civic engagement in digital campaigns because it fosters inclusiveness, ownership, and dialogue. However, barriers such as digital inequality and participation fatigue must be addressed for sustained impact.

The study justified that the effectiveness of digital social transformation efforts depends on the integration of strategic communication frameworks, as challenges such as poor coordination, misinformation, and limited resources weaken advocacy outcomes and reduce long-term social influence.

This study contributes to the literature by advancing the scholarly understanding of how communication can be reimagined as a transformative tool for social change in the digital era through the integration of participatory communication approaches and strategic communication frameworks. Unlike previous studies that focused mainly on either the technological dimensions of digital advocacy or the outcomes of online campaigns, this study uniquely examined the interplay between participatory communication, civic engagement, and strategic planning in digital social transformation efforts. This study fills a significant research gap by demonstrating that digital communication alone does not guarantee meaningful social change unless it is grounded in inclusive participation and supported by structured communication strategies. The study also expanded the application of participatory communication theory to contemporary digital activism, showing that participation must go beyond token interactions to incorporate dialogue, shared ownership, and accountability mechanisms. Additionally, it provided empirical evidence from semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, offering context-specific insights relevant to communication scholarship and practice in developing societies.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made.

1) Government communication agencies and civil society organizations should develop digital communication frameworks to guide social change campaigns and enhance their planning and sustainability.

2) To strengthen civic engagement in digital advocacy, non-governmental organizations and community-based groups should adopt participatory communication approaches that promote inclusiveness and dialogue.

3) Policymakers, donor agencies, and digital advocacy networks should provide capacity-building, funding support, and coordination mechanisms to address the challenges that limit the effective integration of strategic communication in social transformation efforts.

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